

FIELD SCREENING OF BRINJAL VARIETIES/GENOTYPES FOR SUSCEPTIBILITY TO APHID (*Aphis gossypii*) INFESTATIONM.A. Laichattiar^{1*} and R.S. Meena²¹*Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, Parul University, Vadodara- 391760-Gujarat, India.²Department of Entomology and Agricultural Zoology,

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Abstract:

Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) is a widely cultivated vegetable crop valued for its nutritional benefits and adaptability to diverse agro-climatic conditions. However, its productivity is severely threatened by sucking insect pests such as aphids (*Aphis gossypii*) which not only reduce yield and quality but also act as vectors of diseases. This study aimed to evaluate the comparative susceptibility of thirteen brinjal genotypes—IVBL-116-131, JB-8, DBR-31, HABR-4, JB-64, JB-15, Azad Kranti, TRB-9, DBL-9, Surya, Swarna Mani, Kashi Taru, and Punjab Sadabahar—to aphids under field conditions. The experiment was conducted at the Agricultural Research Farm, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, using a Randomized Block Design (RBD) with three replications and carried out during the Kharif seasons of 2014–15. Weekly observations on aphids incidence were recorded from three leaves (top, middle, bottom) of five randomly selected and tagged plants per plot. Results revealed significant variation in aphid infestation across genotypes. DBR-31 exhibited the highest aphid population (7.30 aphids per three leaves), followed by JB-8 (7.00), whereas Kashi Taru recorded the lowest (3.27), statistically at par with TRB-9 and DBL-9. No genotype was entirely free from infestation, indicating partial resistance or tolerance in select genotypes. These findings highlight the potential for using relatively resistant genotypes in integrated pest management (IPM) strategies to reduce reliance on chemical pesticides.

Keywords: Brinjal genotypes, Sucking insect pest, Aphids (*Aphis gossypii*), Resistance screening, Integrated pest management (IPM)

Introduction:

Vegetables are a vital component of human nutrition and health, offering essential minerals, vitamins, antioxidants, micronutrients, and dietary fiber. Their cultivation represents a significant aspect of agricultural economies, particularly in developing nations. Among these, brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.), commonly referred to as eggplant, is a widely cultivated and consumed vegetable in tropical and subtropical regions. Belonging to the family *Solanaceae*, brinjal holds considerable importance across various parts of the world, including Central, South, and Southeast Asia, as well as in regions of Africa and Central America (Harish et al., 2011). It contains high amount of carbohydrates (6.4%), protein (1.3%), fat (0.3%), calcium (0.02%), phosphorus (0.02%), iron (0.0013%) and other mineral matters. Apart from its nutritional value, brinjal has also been used in traditional medicinal purpose. For example, tissue extract have been used for treatment of asthma, bronchitis, cholera and drop in blood cholesterol level. (Kashyap et al., 2003). It is often referred to as poor man's vegetable because of its sky-scraping production (Kumar et al., 2014). Hence, it is a good source of income to small and marginal farmers. However, brinjal cultivation faces significant challenges due to infestations by various insect pests, particularly sucking pests such as aphids (*Aphis gossypii*), whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci*), and leafhoppers (*Amrasca biguttula biguttula*). The symptoms described—leaf crinkling, yellowing, deformation, and the development of sooty mould—are characteristic of aphid (*Aphis gossypii*) infestations on brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.). These pests are known to feed on the undersides of leaves, leading to the mentioned symptoms and acting as vectors for various plant diseases leading to substantial yield losses and reduced fruit quality. (Habib et al. 2015 & Tripathy et al.2020). The reliance on chemical pesticides for managing these pests has led to several issues, including the development of pest resistance, resurgence of pest populations, and negative impacts on non-target organisms and the environment. Consequently, there is an urgent need to explore sustainable pest management strategies. One such approach is the identification and cultivation of brinjal genotypes that exhibit natural resistance or tolerance to this pests. In this context, the present study aims to conduct a comparative assessment of various brinjal varieties/genotypes to determine their resistance or susceptibility to aphids. By identifying genotypes with inherent resistance, this research seeks to contribute to the development of sustainable pest management strategies, reduce dependence on chemical pesticides, and promote environmentally friendly agricultural practices.

Material And Methods:

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A field experiment was conducted at the Agricultural Research Farm, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, to assess the tolerance level of selected brinjal varieties/genotypes—namely IVBL-116-131, JB-8, DBR-31, HABR-4, JB-64, JB-15, Azad Kranti, TRB-9, DBL-9, Surya, Swarna Mani, Kashi Taru, and Punjab Sadabahar against key Sucking Insect Pests of brinjal. The objective was to assess their response to infestation of aphids. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) with three replications and carried out during the Kharif seasons of 2014–15. Aphids infestation data were collected weekly from five randomly selected and tagged plants in each plot. For each selected plant, three leaves—one each from the top, middle, and bottom canopy—were carefully examined during the early morning hours when pest activity was minimal. The presence of nymphs and adults of aphids was recorded to evaluate the degree of infestation across different genotypes. The data thus obtained on counts of aphids was analyzed statistically by using square root transformation. Statistical analysis after appropriate transformation of data was undertaken as per Gomez and Gomez (1984).

Results And Discussions:

The data on the screening of different varieties/genotypes of brinjal against *Aphis gossypii* at the weekly interval during 2014-15 were presented in Table and observed that aphid population was significantly influenced by different varieties/genotypes under the present study. It is evident from the data that none of the brinjal varieties/genotypes was completely free from the attack of aphid population. The aphid population was observed two weeks after transplanting of the brinjal seedlings in some varieties/genotypes *i.e.*, 32nd SMW (Standard Metrological Week) and gradually increased and attained the peak population. At 41st SMW of observation, the significantly highest aphid population was recorded from DBR- 31 (18.33 per three leaves) followed by JB-8 (16.03 per three leaves) which was significantly at par with Azad Kranti (15.63 per three leaves). The lowest aphid population was observed on Kashi Taru (9.78 per three leaves) which was at par with HABR-4, TRB-9, Punjab Sadabahar and IVBL-116-131 (9.87, 10.00, 10.03 and 10.33 per three leaves, respectively). Thereafter aphid population gradually declined but remained on crop up to the 3rd week of December (51st SMW).

The overall mean data pertaining to 2014-15 presented in Table and illustrated in Fig. revealed that the highest aphid population was observed in DBR-31 (7.30 per three leaves) which was found at par with JB-8 (7.00 per three leaves) and the lowest population was recorded from Kashi Taru (3.27 per three leaves) which was at par with TRB-9 (3.33 per three leaves) and DBL-9 (3.87 per three leaves)

among all varieties/genotypes. The rest of the varieties/genotypes showed moderate aphid population (4.67 to 5.80 per three leaves).

The present findings are in accordance with the findings of Jyani *et al.* (1995) observed that none of the brinjal varieties showed resistance to *Aphis gossypii*. Reddy and Srinivasa (2001) revealed that Arka Sheel had the highest number of aphids, while Pusa Purple Round had the lowest. During summer, Arka Keshav and Green Long had the lowest and highest number of aphids, respectively. However, Patel *et al.* (1995) tested twenty-eight varieties of brinjal for screening of resistance to insect pests. Of these, the varieties Manjari Gota, B-47, Local green, Pusa Kranti, Arka Kusumkar and S-71-21-4-22 to *Aphis gossypii* were found comparatively resistance. Mukhopadhyay and Mandal (1994) evaluated 41 cultivars of brinjal to the cotton aphid (*Aphis gossypii*) there was significant differences in reaction to the aphids were observed among the cultivars, although no cultivars were observed to be resistant aphids. However, Navkiran showed tolerance. This fluctuating trend in various seasons due to inherited characters of genotypes as well as environmental conditions. As the crop advanced the incidence in population of aphid also showed an increasing trend. There was no earlier report on selected genotypes to support the present investigation.

Conclusion:

The present study clearly demonstrated significant variability among the evaluated brinjal varieties/genotypes in their response to infestation of aphids, *Aphis gossypii*. Although none of the genotypes exhibited complete resistance, genotypes such as Kashi Taru, TRB-9, and DBL-9 showed comparatively lower levels of aphid infestation, indicating their potential tolerance. On the other hand, DBR-31 and JB-8 were found to be more susceptible, recording the highest pest populations. The findings suggest that varietal selection can play a crucial role in minimizing pest pressure and reducing dependence on chemical pesticides. Incorporating tolerant genotypes into integrated pest management (IPM) programs offers a promising and sustainable approach to brinjal cultivation.

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Table : Screening of different brinjal varieties/genotypes against *Aphis gossypii* under field conditions during 2014-15

Tr. No	Average* number of aphids per 3 leaves at different standard metrological weeks																				Overall mean
	32 SMW	33 SMW	34 SMW	35 SMW	36 SMW	37 SMW	38 SMW	39 SMW	40 SMW	41 SMW	42 SMW	43 SMW	44 SMW	45 SMW	46 SMW	47 SMW	48 SMW	49 SMW	50 SMW	51 SMW	
T ₁	0.00 (0.71)	0.87 (1.17)	2.50 (1.71)	3.63 (2.00)	4.20 (2.13)	5.33 (2.39)	6.50 (2.65)	7.50 (2.83)	9.00 (3.08)	10.33 (3.29)	13.87 (3.78)	11.00 (3.37)	9.50 (3.14)	6.54 (2.64)	5.67 (2.47)	3.33 (1.93)	2.87 (1.81)	1.50 (1.36)	1.00 (1.20)	0.83 (1.14)	5.30 (2.41)
T ₂	0.83 (1.15)	2.00 (1.56)	3.20 (1.90)	5.50 (2.44)	6.83 (2.70)	8.20 (2.94)	11.00 (3.37)	12.33 (3.57)	14.20 (3.83)	16.03 (4.06)	14.00 (3.80)	12.27 (3.57)	9.10 (3.08)	7.20 (2.76)	4.87 (2.30)	3.83 (2.07)	3.00 (1.85)	2.54 (1.72)	1.87 (1.51)	1.20 (1.29)	7.00 (2.74)
T ₃	1.00 (1.22)	2.33 (1.67)	3.00 (1.87)	5.63 (2.46)	6.50 (2.62)	8.00 (2.92)	10.36 (3.28)	12.10 (3.55)	14.56 (3.87)	18.33 (4.34)	15.20 (3.96)	13.40 (3.73)	10.76 (3.36)	7.40 (2.81)	5.20 (2.37)	4.00 (2.11)	3.63 (2.02)	2.00 (1.55)	1.63 (1.42)	1.00 (1.20)	7.30 (2.79)
T ₄	0.30 (0.90)	1.00 (1.22)	2.03 (1.59)	3.20 (1.92)	3.87 (2.09)	5.60 (2.47)	6.60 (2.66)	7.20 (2.76)	8.50 (3.00)	9.87 (3.22)	12.50 (3.61)	10.00 (3.22)	8.40 (2.98)	6.33 (2.61)	5.00 (2.34)	3.33 (1.96)	2.50 (1.73)	1.87 (1.54)	1.20 (1.30)	0.60 (1.05)	5.00 (2.34)
T ₅	0.20 (0.84)	0.50 (1.00)	1.00 (1.23)	2.33 (1.68)	3.33 (1.96)	4.00 (2.12)	5.63 (2.48)	7.20 (2.77)	8.50 (3.00)	14.30 (3.85)	11.83 (3.51)	9.87 (3.22)	6.50 (2.65)	4.33 (2.20)	3.67 (2.04)	3.00 (1.87)	2.87 (1.83)	2.50 (1.73)	1.03 (1.24)	0.90 (1.18)	4.67 (2.27)
T ₆	1.20 (1.27)	1.83 (1.53)	2.50 (1.73)	3.63 (2.03)	4.87 (2.32)	5.33 (2.41)	6.93 (2.73)	8.03 (2.92)	10.87 (3.37)	12.00 (3.53)	14.20 (3.83)	11.50 (3.46)	8.67 (3.03)	6.50 (2.65)	4.20 (2.17)	3.33 (1.96)	2.87 (1.78)	2.00 (1.58)	1.03 (1.24)	0.50 (0.99)	5.60 (2.47)
T ₇	1.00 (1.20)	1.20 (1.30)	3.00 (1.87)	4.00 (2.12)	5.20 (2.39)	6.33 (2.61)	7.87 (2.89)	9.60 (3.18)	11.50 (3.46)	15.63 (4.02)	12.00 (3.54)	10.63 (3.34)	8.76 (3.04)	6.50 (2.65)	4.10 (2.14)	3.33 (1.96)	2.63 (1.77)	1.30 (1.34)	1.00 (1.22)	0.40 (0.95)	5.80 (2.51)
T ₈	0.00 (0.71)	0.63 (1.06)	1.20 (1.30)	1.90 (1.55)	2.50 (1.73)	3.33 (1.95)	5.80 (2.51)	6.87 (2.71)	7.50 (2.83)	10.00 (3.24)	6.00 (2.55)	5.33 (2.41)	4.00 (2.12)	3.50 (2.00)	2.93 (1.85)	2.20 (1.64)	1.20 (1.30)	0.87 (1.17)	0.60 (1.05)	0.20 (0.84)	3.33 (1.96)
T ₉	0.50 (1.00)	0.87 (1.17)	1.50 (1.41)	2.20 (1.64)	3.00 (1.87)	3.87 (2.09)	5.00 (2.34)	6.50 (2.65)	8.20 (2.95)	11.87 (3.52)	9.00 (3.08)	6.50 (2.65)	5.80 (2.51)	4.20 (2.17)	3.00 (1.87)	2.40 (1.70)	1.50 (1.41)	0.87 (1.17)	0.50 (0.99)	0.00 (0.71)	3.87 (2.08)
T ₁₀	1.03 (1.23)	1.50 (1.41)	2.33 (1.68)	3.50 (2.00)	4.90 (2.32)	5.67 (2.48)	6.50 (2.65)	8.00 (2.91)	10.03 (3.24)	14.00 (3.81)	12.53 (3.61)	9.58 (3.17)	8.00 (2.91)	6.33 (2.61)	4.50 (2.24)	3.63 (2.03)	2.50 (1.73)	1.87 (1.54)	1.20 (1.30)	1.00 (1.22)	5.43 (2.44)
T ₁₁	0.50 (1.00)	0.87 (1.17)	1.20 (1.30)	2.10 (1.61)	3.00 (1.87)	4.50 (2.24)	6.00 (2.55)	7.67 (2.86)	9.83 (3.21)	11.50 (3.46)	13.50 (3.74)	10.63 (3.34)	6.33 (2.61)	4.20 (2.17)	3.10 (1.90)	2.50 (1.73)	1.20 (1.30)	1.03 (1.23)	0.33 (0.91)	0.00 (0.71)	4.50 (2.24)
T ₁₂	0.40 (0.95)	0.80 (1.14)	1.12 (1.27)	1.40 (1.38)	2.30 (1.67)	2.80 (1.82)	3.45 (1.99)	5.36 (2.42)	6.45 (2.64)	9.78 (3.21)	7.20 (2.77)	6.10 (2.57)	5.10 (2.37)	4.00 (2.12)	3.20 (1.92)	2.03 (1.59)	1.67 (1.47)	1.03 (1.23)	0.67 (1.08)	0.50 (1.00)	3.27 (1.94)
T ₁₃	0.50 (1.00)	0.83 (1.15)	2.50 (1.73)	4.00 (2.12)	4.87 (2.32)	5.50 (2.45)	6.40 (2.63)	8.33 (2.97)	9.00 (3.08)	10.03 (3.24)	11.50 (3.46)	8.60 (3.02)	7.00 (2.74)	6.33 (2.61)	5.20 (2.39)	4.67 (2.27)	4.00 (2.12)	3.00 (1.87)	2.93 (1.85)	1.50 (1.41)	5.33 (2.41)
SEm±	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.12	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.07	0.06
C.D at 5%	0.23	0.22	0.27	0.28	0.36	0.25	0.27	0.29	0.20	0.20	0.23	0.32	0.31	0.24	0.28	0.29	0.36	0.34	0.33	0.20	0.19

Figures in the parenthesis are $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformed values (Where x = Actual number)

Average* of three replications

SMW = Standard metrological week

T₁: IVBL-116-131, T₂: JB-8, T₃: DBR-31, T₄: HABR-4, T₅: JB-64, T₆: JB-15, T₇: AZAD KRANTI, T₈: TRB-9, T₉: DBL-9, T₁₀: SURYA, T₁₁: SWARNA MANI, T₁₂: KASHI TARU and T₁₃: PUNJAB SADABAHAR

Fig. Aphid infestation in different brinjal varieties/genotypes during 2014-15